

Imaging Findings in Gorlin-Goltz Syndrome: A Case SeriesSaurya^{1,3}, Srishti Sharma², Bhumika Dhamija³¹Senior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, AIIMS, Patna²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, AIIMS, Patna³Junior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, AIIMS, Patna

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Abstract:**Background:** Gorlin-Goltz Syndrome (GGS), or Nevoid Basal Cell Carcinoma Syndrome (NBCCS), is a rare autosomal dominant disorder characterized by various clinical manifestations. This case series emphasizes the radiological features crucial for diagnosis.**Methods:** We present imaging findings from three cases of NBCCS, focusing on the diagnostic criteria and clinical manifestations.**Results:** All cases exhibited multiple odontogenic keratocysts (OKCs) of the jaw and intracranial calcifications. These radiological features are pivotal for early diagnosis.**Conclusion:** Radiological imaging plays a vital role in diagnosing GGS, aiding in the multidisciplinary management and improved patient outcomes.

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Introduction

Gorlin-Goltz Syndrome (GGS), also known as Nevoid Basal Cell Carcinoma Syndrome (NBCCS), is a rare autosomal dominant disorder with an incidence of approximately 1 in 60,000 live births. It presents a variety of clinical manifestations and is diagnosed based on major and minor criteria as defined by the International Colloquium on Basal Cell Nevus Syndrome [1, 2].

Diagnostic Criteria and Clinical Manifestations

The major criteria include:

1. Basal Cell Carcinomas (BCCs) prior to age 20 or an excessive number of BCCs disproportionate to prior sun exposure and skin type.
2. Odontogenic Keratocysts (OKCs) of the jaw prior to age 20.
3. Palmar or plantar pitting.
4. Lamellar calcification of the falx cerebri.
5. Medulloblastoma, typically desmoplastic.
6. A first-degree relative with NBCCS.

The minor criteria include:

1. Rib anomalies.
2. Other specific skeletal malformations and radiologic changes (e.g., vertebral anomalies, kyphoscoliosis, short fourth metacarpals, post-axial polydactyly).
3. Macrocephaly.

4. Cleft lip/palate.
5. Ovarian or cardiac fibroma.
6. Lymphomesenteric cysts.
7. Ocular abnormalities (e.g., strabismus, hyper-telorum, congenital cataracts, glaucoma, coloboma).

A diagnosis of GGS can be made when either two major criteria are met, or one major and two minor criteria are met [3].

Case Reports**Case I**

A 20 year-old male presented with facial asymmetry, and multiple jaw swellings which has progressed over past one year. Clinical examination showed multiple swellings involving mandible and maxilla. Palmar and plantar pits were also seen. NCCT face was done which revealed multiple cystic expansile lesion with unerupted tooth s/o OKC's. Based on the findings Possibility of GGS was considered. CT head was done which revealed calcification along falx.

Incisional biopsy from the cystic jaw lesions confirmed it to be odontogenic keratocyst, hence two major criteria were fulfilled and diagnosis of Gorlin Goltz syndrome were fulfilled and diagnosis was made.

Figure 1: CT face bone window showing multiple cystic expansile lesion with unerupted tooth s/o OKC's. In same patient falx and tentorial calcification was also seen (White arrows)

Case II

A 18-year-old boy presented with complaint of multiple swelling in cheek and upper and lower jaw region that gradually increased in size over a period of 6 months. Swellings were, non-tender and soft to rubbery in consistency on palpation. Past medical history was unremarkable. NCCT face and head

was done which revealed multiple expansile cystic lesions in maxilla and mandible with unerupted tooth and falx calcification.

Enucleation of all the cysts along with associated impacted tooth buds was carried out, histological analysis confirmed lesions to be odontogenic keratocysts.

Figure 2: This case also show multiple OKC in maxilla and mandible (thick white arrows). In same case falx calcification was also seen (white arrow)

Case III: A 20-year-old female patient presented with multiple pigmented lesions over her face and chest and multiple jaw swellings. These lesions were small initially and had gradually increased in size. NCCT face and head revealed tentorial and

falx calcification WITH associated multiple cystic lesion in maxilla and mandible with unerupted teeth. Histopathological evaluation of a one of the pigmented papules showed findings consistent with BCC.

Figure 3: Another case of Gorlin Goltz syndrome CT face showing tentorial and falx calcification (thin white arrow) with associated multiple cystic lesion in maxilla with unerupted teeth s/o OKC'S (thick white arrow)

Discussion

The radiological findings in all cases included multiple OKCs involving the maxilla and mandible with falx cerebri and tentorial calcifications. These features are critical in the identification and diagnosis of GGS.

The presence of OKCs is often the first clinical feature and a pivotal diagnostic marker in young patients. In addition to OKCs, intracranial calcifications, particularly in the falx cerebri and tentorium, are highly associated with GGS. These calcifications can be readily identified on CT scans and are significant diagnostic criteria [4-6].

Conclusion

This case series highlights the vital role of radiological imaging in diagnosing Gorlin-Goltz Syndrome. The identification of characteristic imaging findings such as multiple odontogenic keratocysts, intracranial calcifications, and skeletal anomalies is

crucial for early diagnosis and effective management of GGS. Radiologists play a key role in the multidisciplinary approach required for the comprehensive care of patients with GGS, contributing to improved patient outcomes through accurate diagnosis and timely intervention.

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